

Study of molecular interactions of copper oxide nanoparticles with 10% aqueous ethylene glycol at different temperatures : Using physicochemical method[†]

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Abstract : In this investigation copper oxide (CuO) nanoparticles were synthesized by precipitation method using $[\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ as a starting material. The synthesized nanoparticles were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The synthesized nanoparticles were dispersed in an aqueous solution of ethylene glycol in various concentrations with the help of ultrasonicator to obtain nanofluids of different concentrations. Density (ρ), ultrasonic velocity (u) and viscosity (η) for these nanofluids were experimentally measured as a function of temperatures ($T = 303.15 \text{ K}$, 308.15 K and 313.15 K). Using these experimentally determined values various acoustic and thermodynamic parameters were evaluated.

Keywords : CuO nanoparticles, base fluid, ultrasonic velocity, density, viscosity, acoustical parameters.

Introduction

In the past decades, metal oxide nanoparticles are extensively used in wide range of technological applications. Transition metal oxide nanoparticles play a key role in many areas of research (i.e. in chemistry, physics and material science¹). The coinage metal oxide nano-particles exhibit unique chemical properties because of their small size and high density². Nanoparticles have wide range of applications in miscellaneous fields, including chemical manufacturing, energy conversion and storage, biological applications and environmental technology^{3,4}.

Lot of work on nanohybrids deals with solid state materials. In 1995 Choi, gave concept of nanofluids⁵. Nanofluids containing small amount of metal or metal oxide nanoparticles reveal considerably better thermal conductivity compared to the base fluids⁶. Thermal conductivity of nanofluid plays imperative role in the development of energy-efficient heat transfer

appliances. The thermal conductivities of various fluids like water, ethylene glycol and engine oil are comparatively lower than those of solid particles. Now a day, there is strong need of development of superior heat transfer fluids with higher thermal conductivity. When a small amount of nanoparticle is dispersed uniformly in a host fluid (e.g. heat transfer fluids like water, ethylene glycol, etc.) this results spectacular enhancement in the thermal properties of host fluids. The major problem arises in this suspension is the instability of nanofluids, this is due to the agglomeration of nanoparticles dispersed in base fluids. Thus in order to prepare stable nano-suspension ultrasonication plays a very important role to disperse aggregated nanoparticles⁷. In our present work CuO nanoparticles were synthesized and dispersed in base fluids. Among transition metal oxides, CuO nanoparticles were chosen because of the wide range of applications in high temperature superconductors, metallurgy and in heat

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transfer applications⁸⁻¹⁰. CuO is a p-type semiconductor like CuS and can be used in various electronic devices^{11,12}. Various methods reported in literature for the synthesis of CuO NPs like electrochemical method, one-step solid state reaction method, sol-gel technique, sonochemical method, thermal decomposition of precursors, etc.

Ultrasonic velocity, density and rheological studies play an imperative role in understanding solute-solvent, solvent-solvent and solute-solute interactions in aqueous and non-aqueous medium^{13,14}.

Although the thermal conductivity is the most interesting property for practical purposes, less attention has been paid so far to other properties such as density and viscosity of nanofluids. Cheng *et al.* pointed out that these properties should be determined for their effects on nanofluid flow and heat transfer characteristics¹⁵. A comparison between the experimental viscosity ratios and results predicted by Batchelor and Wang models for magnetite nanofluids was reported by Toghraie *et al.* and they observed that, theoretical models are unable to predict viscosity of the magnetite nanofluids¹⁶. The dynamic viscosity of alumina-engine oil nanofluid in different solid volume fractions and temperature was experimentally investigated by Esfe *et al.*¹⁷. Esfe *et al.* performed ZnO-EG nanofluids thermal conductivity using MLP neural networks. They showed that neural networks can estimate the experimental results with a high precision¹⁸. An examination of viscosity of MWCNTs/ZnO-SAE40 hybrid nano-lubricants under various temperatures and solid volume fractions is presented by Hemmat Esfe *et al.* Viscosity measurements showed that the viscosity decreases with increasing temperature and increases with an enhancement in the solid volume fraction¹⁹.

Close examination of the literature indicates that only some authors studied the ultrasonic properties of nanofluids^{20,21}. Despite recent advances, much more works involving theoretical, experimental and numerical research are necessary to solve the mysteries of nanofluids.

In recent years, many researchers have created

new kinds of fluids by dispersion of nanosized particles in pure water or ethylene glycol. However, few studies have been reported about nanofluids whose base fluid is ethylene glycol and water mixture²²⁻²⁷. Similarly very few studies are available about the nanofluids of propylene glycol or hexylene glycol and water mixtures as base fluids²⁸.

In this paper study on the response of CuO nanoparticles in basefluid to the ultrasonic wave propagation for the basic understanding how these nanoparticles behave in fluids and how they interact with each other and with fluid was carried out. Stable suspensions of nanoparticles were prepared using ultrasonication and were used for attaining a deeper understanding of interparticle (particle-particle) and particle-fluid interactions as functions of concentration and temperature.

Experimental

Synthesis of nanoparticles :

For the synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles, cupric acetate dehydrate [Cu(CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O], glacial acetic acid (CH₃COOH), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), acetone and ethanol are procured from Sigma Aldrich. All the chemicals are of GR-grade and used without any further purification. The synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles is carried out by precipitating copper salt in alkaline medium²⁹. The copper salt solution used is freshly prepared 0.2 M Cu (CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O. The salt solution is mixed with 1 ml glacial acetic acid and the resultant solution is heated at a constant stirring speed of 1000 rpm until required temperature of 60 °C is reached. Higher temperature is favoured because of higher reaction rates, which produces large amounts of nuclei to form in a short time, and the aggregation of crystals is inhibited. Glacial acetic acid is used to prevent the hydrolysis of the copper acetate solution. On vigorous stirring, the above solution pH is increased rapidly to 10.5 by adding NaOH pellets where a black precipitate of CuO is formed instantly. At the same pH, temperature and stirring speed, the solution is kept at a digestion time of 30 min. Overall chemical reaction can be written as

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After cooling to room temperature, particles are separated from the dispersion. The top water layer with excess salts is discarded. The particles are washed with water, ethanol and acetone. They are separated from dispersion by centrifugation at 2500 rpm for 30 min and dried at room temperature in an inert atmosphere.

Preparation of nanofluids :

The nanopowder of CuO thus obtained was dispersed in base fluid, an aqueous solution of ethylene glycol, to obtain nanofluids of different concentrations. Weighing of nanoparticles powder was determined using electronic single pan four digit Mettler Toledo balance (Model ML204) with an accuracy of 0.1 mg. To achieve uniform dispersion of the particles ultrasonic wave of frequency 4 MHz was passed through the nanofluid for 2 h with the help of ultrasonicator. It is evident that the ultrasonic treatment to the fluids increases the settling time of the suspension.

Characterization :

The synthesized nanoparticles were characterized by using various techniques like X-ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). In the present study, Bruker AXS D₈ Advance X-ray diffractometer was used to obtain X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples. JEOL JEM-2100 LaB₆ was used for TEM studies.

To examine the morphology of the synthesized nanoparticles, SEM analysis was carried out on the JEOL JSM-6390LV SEM fitted with secondary electron detector, and equipped with an attachment for the energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) to enable elemental composition analysis.

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) was used to find the average hydrodynamic size of the synthesized CuO nanoparticles.

Results and discussion

The characterization of nanoparticles was done by various techniques as described above and these nanoparticles were dispersed in base fluids. The values of ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity of nanofluids were experimental determined. These values help us to evaluate various acoustical parameters.

Characterization :

The XRD pattern of synthesized nanoparticles is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of CuO nanoparticles.

All diffraction peaks can be indexed as the monoclinic crystal structure of CuO (space group C2/c) by comparison with data from JCPDS file no. 48-1548 with lattice constants $a = 4.6837 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 3.4226 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 5.1288 \text{ \AA}$ and $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 99.54^\circ$, $\gamma = 90^\circ$ no characteristic peaks of any other impurity were observed. The sharp peaks indicate that the product was well crystallized. Debye-Scherrer equation was used for calculating the crystallite size. The crystallite size corresponding to most intense peak was found to be 14.692(0.005) nm corresponding to 2θ value of 38.7832 and hkl (111). TEM micrograph of the synthesized nanoparticles is depicted in Fig. 2.

Average diameter of the nanoparticles was 15-20 nm evaluated by ImageJ software. SEM and EDX of the synthesized nanoparticles are depicted in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively. SEM image showed that the obtained nanoparticles were agglomerated to a large extent and the particles have flower like morphology.

The stoichiometry of sample was examined by EDX

Fig. 2. TEM micrograph of CuO nanoparticles.

spectrum. Only Cu and O signals have been detected, suggesting that the nanoparticles were only made up of Cu and O. Weight percentage of Cu was found to be 78.95 and that of O was 19.68. Thus the atomic ratio of Cu and O was 1 : 1.

Fig. 3. SEM image of CuO nanoparticles.

Dynamic light scattering was used to find the average hydrodynamic size of the synthesized CuO nanoparticles. The size determined by DLS was found to be much larger than the size determined by XRD and TEM. By DLS we get the hydrodynamic radius of the particle whereas by TEM we get an estimation of the projected area diameter. When a dispersed particle moves through a liquid medium, a thin layer of the solvent adheres to its surface. This layer influ-

Fig. 4. EDX spectrum of CuO nanoparticles.

ences the movement of the particle in the medium. Thus the hydrodynamic diameter gives us information of the inorganic core along with any coating material and the solvent layer attached to the particle as it moves under the influence of Brownian motion. While estimating size by TEM, this hydration layer is not present hence, we get information only about the inorganic core. Size distribution by intensity of different concentrations of CuO nanoparticles dispersed in 10% aqueous solution of ethylene glycol are shown in Figs. 5–9. In case of nanofluids having concentration of CuO between 0.02–0.08 wt% the result quality was found to be good which means the particles were well dispersed and not agglomerated as shown in Figs. 5–8. But in case of nanofluids having 0.10

Fig. 5. Size distribution by intensity of 0.02 wt% CuO nanoparticles in 10% aqueous ethylene glycol.

Fig. 6. Size distribution by intensity of 0.04 wt% CuO nanoparticles in 10% aqueous ethylene glycol.

Fig. 8. Size distribution by intensity of 0.08 wt% CuO nanoparticles in 10% aqueous ethylene glycol.

Fig. 7. Size distribution by intensity of 0.06 wt% CuO nanoparticles in 10% aqueous ethylene glycol.

Fig. 9. Size distribution by intensity of 0.10 wt% CuO nanoparticles in 10% aqueous ethylene glycol.

wt% concentration of CuO the result quality was not found to be good and z-average was abruptly increases to 1061 nm which indicates agglomeration of nanoparticles.

Acoustical studies of nanofluids :

An ultrasonic interferometer provided by Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi was used to evaluate ultrasonic velocity of nanofluids. Ultrasonic velocity was measured at a frequency of 5 MHz. Viscosity was measured by using Ostwald’s viscometer. The density of various nanofluids was automatically measured using Anton Paar densimeter (DMA 5000 M, Aus-

tria). The temperature was automatically controlled to $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$ K by a built-in Peltier device. All these measurements were performed for the nanofluids of different concentrations at three different temperatures 303.15 K, 308.15 K and 313.15 K. By using these experimentally determined values various acoustical parameters were evaluated, that gives information regarding type of interactions present in our system. Table 1 shows the experimentally determined values of ultrasonic velocity (u), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) of nanofluids. From the data recorded in Table 1, it has been observed that there occurs an

Table 1. Ultrasonic velocity (u), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) of nanofluids having different concentrations of CuO in 10% aq. ethylene glycol at three different temperatures

Temp. (K)	Conc. (wt%)	$u \times 10^{-3}$ (m s ⁻¹)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	$\eta \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
303.15	0	1.54909	1.00911	1.14316
	0.02	1.55145	1.00962	1.17486
	0.04	1.55373	1.00972	1.19975
	0.06	1.55138	1.01015	1.17785
	0.08	1.54918	1.01073	1.15719
	0.10	1.55150	1.01046	1.17405
308.15	0	1.55528	1.00726	1.05367
	0.02	1.55736	1.00779	1.08517
	0.04	1.55989	1.00789	1.11345
	0.06	1.55796	1.00831	1.09189
	0.08	1.55582	1.00891	1.07273
	0.10	1.55797	1.00861	1.09291
313.15	0	1.56180	1.00523	0.98043
	0.02	1.56362	1.00576	1.01597
	0.04	1.56582	1.00587	1.03555
	0.06	1.56336	1.00628	1.01469
	0.08	1.56178	1.00693	0.99701
	0.10	1.56364	1.00658	1.01053

increase in ultrasonic velocity (Fig. 10) and viscosity (Fig. 12) upto some concentration of CuO nanoparticles after that their values start decreasing and finally a little increase occurs in these values.

By using these experimentally determined values various acoustic parameters were evaluated like adiabatic compressibility (β_{ad}), intermolecular free length (L_f), relaxation time (τ) and attenuation coefficient (α/f^2). Adiabatic compressibility (β_{ad}) of the samples was calculated from the speed of sound (u) and the density of the medium (ρ) using the Newton Laplace relation^{30,31}.

$$\beta_{ad} = 1/\rho u^2 \quad (1)$$

The intermolecular free length (L_f) was calculated using the following formula given by Jacobson^{32,33}

$$L_f = K_T \beta_{ad}^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where, K_T is Jacobson's constant.

The relaxation time (τ) can be calculated from the relation

$$\tau = (4/3)\beta_{ad}\eta \quad (3)$$

Fig. 10. Plots of ultrasonic velocity of various nanofluids of CuO in 10% aqueous ethylene glycol at different temperatures.

Fig. 11. Plots of density of various nanofluids of CuO in 10% aqueous ethylene glycol at different temperatures.

Attenuation coefficient (α/f^2) was evaluated from the values of speed of sound and relaxation time by using Stokes relation³⁴

$$\alpha/f^2 = 4n^2 \tau/2u \quad (4)$$

Table 2 shows the values of adiabatic compressibility, intermolecular free length, relaxation time and attenuation coefficient.

The increase in ultrasonic velocity and viscosity at lower concentration of CuO nanoparticles is due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding among CuO nanoparticles, ethylene glycol and water molecules

Fig. 12. Plots of viscosity of various nanofluids of CuO in 10% aqueous ethylene glycol at different temperatures.

Fig. 13. Plots of adiabatic compressibility of various nanofluids of CuO in 10% aqueous ethylene glycol at different temperatures.

(CuO-EG-H₂O) as a result of this bonding overall compressibility of the medium decreases and hence ultrasonic velocity and viscosity increases. But above a particular concentration of CuO nanoparticles their

interactions with glycol (CuO-EG) and water molecules (CuO-H₂O) increases which in turn start decreasing the hydrogen bonding between glycol and water molecules (EG-H₂O) as a result overall com-

Table 2. Adiabatic compressibility (β_{ad}), intermolecular free length (L_f), relaxation time (τ), and attenuation coefficient (α/f^2) of nanofluids having different concentrations of CuO in 10% aq. ethylene glycol at three different temperatures

Temp. (K)	Conc. (wt%)	$\beta_{ad} \times 10^{10}$ (m kg ⁻¹ s)	$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	$\tau \times 10^{13}$ (s)	$\alpha/f^2 \times 10^{-14}$ (s ² m ⁻¹)
303.15	0	4.12961	4.21670	6.29441	8.01248
	0.02	4.11497	4.20922	6.44602	8.19300
	0.04	4.10250	4.20283	6.56263	8.32898
	0.06	4.11320	4.20831	6.45964	8.21068
	0.08	4.12250	4.21307	6.36069	8.09640
	0.10	4.11130	4.20734	6.43583	8.17978
308.15	0	4.10433	4.24176	5.76612	7.31079
	0.02	4.09121	4.23497	5.91955	7.49529
	0.04	4.07755	4.22790	6.05354	7.65252
	0.06	4.08596	4.23225	5.94856	7.52914
	0.08	4.09478	4.23682	5.85676	7.42314
	0.10	4.08469	4.23160	5.95226	7.53377
313.15	0	4.07836	4.26618	5.33138	6.73137
	0.02	4.06671	4.26009	5.50887	6.94738
	0.04	4.05487	4.25388	5.59870	7.05075
	0.06	4.06594	4.25968	5.50092	6.93851
	0.08	4.07156	4.26263	5.41252	6.83390
	0.10	4.06329	4.25829	5.47476	6.90427

compressibility of the medium increases (Fig. 10) and hence ultrasonic velocity and viscosity decreases. At some higher concentration (0.10 wt%) of CuO nanoparticles they start aggregating due to inter particle interactions (CuO-CuO) and hence their interactions with glycol (CuO-EG) and water molecules (CuO-H₂O) decrease. Due to this the hydrogen bonding between glycol and water molecules (EG-H₂O) increases and hence a little increase occurs in the values of ultrasonic velocity and viscosity. There occurs an increase in density (Fig. 11) with increase in concentration of CuO nanoparticles. The variation of

Fig. 14. Plots of intermolecular free length of various nanofluids of CuO in 10% aqueous ethylene glycol at different temperatures.

Fig. 15. Plots of relaxation time of various nanofluids of CuO in 10% aqueous ethylene glycol at different temperatures.

Fig. 16. Plots of attenuation coefficient of various nanofluids of CuO in 10% aqueous ethylene glycol at different temperatures.

ultrasonic velocity in any solution depends upon the increase or decrease of intermolecular free lengths after mixing the component. As the free length decreases (Fig. 14) due to the increase in concentrations of CuO nanoparticles upto some concentration, ultrasonic velocity increases, it indicates significant interactions between the solute-solvent molecules suggesting a structure promoting tendency of the added solute. But at some higher concentration of CuO nanoparticles, free length starts increasing due to decreasing interactions between glycol and water molecules hence ultrasonic velocity start decreasing. At still higher concentration of nanoparticles due to inter particle interactions the glycol water interactions increases indicated by decrease in intermolecular free length and increase in ultrasonic velocity. Adiabatic compressibility also shows the same trend as that of intermolecular free length with increase in concentration of nanoparticles. Density shows an increase with increase in concentration of nanoparticles. The trends of variation of relaxation time (Fig. 15) and attenuation coefficient (Fig. 16) with increase in concentration of nanoparticles are same as that of ultrasonic velocity and viscosity.

Conclusion

Ultrasonic velocity, density, viscosity, relaxation time and attenuation coefficient showed an increase

with increase in concentration of CuO nanoparticles upto 0.04 wt% because of increasing molecular interactions among CuO, water and ethylene glycol (CuO-EG-H₂O). After that these parameters showed a decrease with increase in concentration of CuO nanoparticles upto 0.08 wt% because of increasing molecular interactions of CuO with water (CuO-H₂O) and ethylene glycol (CuO-EG) and decreasing molecular interactions between water and ethylene glycol (H₂O-EG). On further increasing the concentration of CuO nanoparticles these parameters start increasing because of agglomeration of nanoparticles which decreases the molecular interactions of CuO with water (CuO-H₂O) and ethylene glycol (CuO-EG). Adiabatic compressibility and intermolecular free length showed an opposite trend with increase in concentration of CuO nanoparticles. It has also been observed that with rise in temperature there occurs an increase in ultrasonic velocity and intermolecular free length while density, viscosity, adiabatic compressibility, relaxation time and attenuation coefficient showed a decreasing trend.

Thus such interactions of nanoparticles with base fluids (particle-fluid interactions) are very helpful in understanding the reasons behind the abnormal enhancements in physical properties and to understand the mechanism of transport of nanoparticles in fluids. The knowledge to these particle-fluid interactions will help to improve the performance of these nanofluids in MEMS and other practical applications.

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